

A Dynamic Gender-barriers Framework to Women's Entrepreneurship: A Competency-based Perspective

Tatiana Somià*

*^aDepartment of Economics and Management, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano,
Bolzano, Italy*

e-mail: TSomia@unibz.it

Tatiana Somià is Marie Słodowska Curie Global Research Fellow and Research Assistant at Free University of Bozen-Bolzano.

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A Dynamic Gender-barriers Framework to Women's Entrepreneurship: A Competency-based Perspective

This paper presents a new dynamic gender-barriers framework that aims to provide an updated, layered, and contextualized view of barriers and seeks to further a holistic understanding of women's entrepreneurship and its evolution. Barriers can be created, developed, or removed, in different areas and at different levels, changing over time. Gender barriers can overlap, cross different levels of analysis, and the removal or strengthening of a barrier can have a domino effect on other elements, generating unintended negative consequences, or creating synergies.

This work focuses attention on individual barriers, related to a lack of specific competencies, and offers recommendations to practitioners, policy makers and ecosystem supporters on how to effectively contribute to the competency development of women entrepreneurs. Strategies and policies to develop the competencies, through experiential entrepreneurship programs and executive coaching initiatives, can produce a ripple effect across different layers of society, contributing to reduce the gender gap.

Keywords: gender-barriers framework, women entrepreneurs' competencies, competency-based approach.

Word count: 2479 (without abstract and references)

1. Introduction

This paper presents a new dynamic gender-barriers framework that aims to provide an updated, layered, and contextualized view of barriers and seeks to further a holistic understanding of women's entrepreneurship and its evolution. Existing research on female entrepreneurs is criticized for adopting an individualistic orientation while rarely discussing the contextual and historical variables (Ahl, 2006). This work expands the focus by developing a framework to consider both individual and contextual aspects.

Adopting a social constructionist perspective, entrepreneurship and its barriers are considered socially embedded, in constant evolution, capable of influencing the shape of the 'future to come' (Pittaway, 2021). Barriers to entrepreneurship, and to female entrepreneurship, change over time, including in response to complex and somewhat unpredictable exogenous phenomena such as the Covid-19 pandemic or the recent Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

The pandemic has had a greater impact on women's entrepreneurship, creating new barriers, especially for those women entrepreneurs who run small businesses, operate food and retail services, and have had to deal with the added responsibilities of family care (Elam et al., 2021). Women entrepreneurs, in fact, tend to operate different types of businesses than men, sometimes choosing sectors that require lower barriers to entry and may allow a better opportunity to manage family and work activities at the same time (Strawser et al., 2021).

Barriers induced by war to international trade affect business, entrepreneurship, and also female entrepreneurship, and can give an impetus to specific industries and their expansion. This happened with the growth of the electronics and aircraft industries caused by World War II and is happening now that we are experiencing new viral global

movements in support of Ukraine that fund local companies and industries (El Tarabishy, 2022; Lakomaa, 2017).

Barriers can be created, developed, or removed, in different areas and at different levels, changing over time. Gender barriers can overlap, (Brush et al., 2009; Wheadon & Duval-Couetil, 2019), cross different levels of analysis, and the removal or strengthening of a barrier can have a domino effect on other elements, generating unintended negative consequences, or creating synergies that reduce gender gaps.

This work takes a closer look on individual barriers related to the lack of specific competencies of women entrepreneurs and how their development can produce a ripple effect on different layers of society.

2. Approach and theoretical background

A social constructionist perspective has been adopted, which considers entrepreneurship to be a socially constructed phenomenon (Welter & Smallbone, 2008) thus drawing attention to the different layers and areas of embeddedness in which entrepreneurial barriers might take place.

This work reviewed existing frameworks, integrated insights from high-profile international studies on the gender gap and from a systematic literature review, with the aims to identify the founding dimensions of a new comprehensive framework.

2.1 Existing frameworks and international studies on gender barriers

The paper reviews existing frameworks of Bates et al. (2007), Brush et al. (2009), Wheadon and Duval- Couetil (2019), and aims to mediate and extend the type and level of barriers identified. Bates et al. (2007) describe three building blocks of business viability and associated barriers (Money, Market and Management) and Brush et al.

(2009) add Motherhood and Meso/Macro environment to this framework. Instead, Wheadon and Duval-Couetil (2019) developed a framework to analyze complex multi-level barriers in technology entrepreneurship.

In addition to the reviewing of main existing frameworks, the work has integrated insights on gender barriers from the Global Gender Gap Report (World Economic Forum, 2021), from the Gender Equality Index (European Commission, 2020) and from the Women’s Entrepreneurship 2020/21 GEM report (Elam et al., 2021). The Global Gender Gap Index examines the gap between men and women at global level taking into account four indicators: economic opportunity, political growth, training, health, and survival. Women’s Entrepreneurship GEM report tracks the evolution of women’s entrepreneurship worldwide, considering many dimensions of entrepreneurship while the Gender Equality Index focuses on the progress of gender equality in the European Union.

The Women's Entrepreneurship GEM Report focuses on gender barriers faced by ventures (market, money and intrapreneurial connections) and female entrepreneurs (e.g.: competencies to start or run a business), while the Global Gender Gap Index and Gender Equality Index primarily examine economic, educational, political, and socio-cultural gender barriers (see Tab. 1).

Tab. 1 Barriers identified by high-quality international studies on gender gap

	VENTURE BARRIERS			SOCIETAL/INSTITUTIONAL BARRIERS				MICRO-BARRIERS
Barriers 5by5 framework	MARKET	MONEY	MANAGEMENT	ECONOMIC	EDUCATIONAL	POLITICAL	SOCIO-CULTURAL	FAMILY & ENTREPRENEUR
GEM Women’s	Business Size & Industry segmentation	Money	Entrepreneurial connections					Competencies to start a new business, self-awareness, self-confidence, fear of failure, etc.
Global Gender Gap (WEF)				Economic Participation & Opportunity	Educational Attainment	Political Empowerment	Health & Survival	
Gender Equality Index		Money		Work	Knowledge	Power	Health	Time

Source: Author’s elaboration

2.2 Literature review on barriers to women's entrepreneurship

A systematic literature review on barriers to women's entrepreneurship is conducted, which adopts procedures similar to those used by other studies focused on women in entrepreneurship (Brush et al., 2009; Greene et al., 2003). The search used the scientific database Scopus (Burnham, 2006) and applied the key words 'female entrepreneur*', 'women entrepreneur*', 'women business', along with 'barrier*' and 'constraint*'.

Relevant articles, published from 2002 to 2021, were used and these were limited to the most frequently cited entrepreneurship peer-reviewed journals in English (Greene et al., 2003). An iterative 'snowballing' technique was used to identify other topically relevant articles not included in the initial sample.

2.2.1 Literature review findings

A preliminary analysis of literature on barriers to women's entrepreneurship deductively coded the content based on the research context, the theories and methods used, the barriers examined, the key findings and the recommendations identified. A second stage of analysis then inductively coded barriers studied to determine any emergent patterns, dimensions, or themes in the research findings. Relevant results were categorized according to the type and level of barriers studied, with the aim to create an updated gender barriers framework for women's entrepreneurship.

From the systematic literature review on barriers to women's entrepreneurship it has emerged that 40% of relevant articles identified focused only on one type of barrier: 13% focused on individual barriers women entrepreneurs face, 11% on "money" barriers, 6% on "management" barriers (networking barriers), 6% on socio-cultural barriers, and 4% on family barriers. The remaining 60% of the papers consider the presence of several types of barriers and at different levels of analysis.

3. A new gender-barriers framework to women' entrepreneurship

The multi-level “5by5¹ Framework” developed encompasses five types of barriers, identified by parts of the circle: 1) *Venture*, 2) *Economic*, 3) *Socio-cultural*, 4) *Political* and 5) *Educational barriers*, and by five levels of analysis represented by the concentric circles: 1) *Mini*, 2) *Micro*, 3) *Meso*, 4) *Macro* and 5) *Mega* (see Fig. 1).

The study began by considering the venture barriers identified by Bates et al. (2007), referred to by Brush et al. (2009) as “3Ms”: “Money”, “Market” and “Management”. Among the three categories, Bates et al. consider the latter the most important defining it as “*skilled and capable entrepreneur, or the management team*” (Bates et al., 2007, p. 10).

The female entrepreneur was placed at the core of the framework, for her relevance, and because the individual represents the smallest level of analysis described as the *mini* level. The study considered the family and its barriers, as in economic analysis, at the *micro* level encompassing the entrepreneur.

The *meso* and *macro* environments, considered together by Brush et al. (2009) 5M framework– in addition to Money, Market, Management and Motherhood– are treated separately in the 5by5 framework, choosing the same approach taken by Ogundana et al. (2021) in their 6M framework. The researchers, extending Brush et al. (2009) framework, developed a gender-based model of growth identifying the manner in which women entrepreneurs in West African setting leveraged the “6 Ms” in growing their enterprises (Ogundana et al., 2021). In their model, money, management and market

¹ The name “5by5” is borrowed from the military. The communication signal quality is reported on two scales from 1 to 5: strength (1st number) and clarity (2nd number). Five by five therefore means a signal which has excellent strength and perfect clarity. The aim of this Framework is to be the most understandable “signal” possible.

have a direct effect on growth, while motherhood, meso-environment, and macro-environment are the indirect determinants of growth, mediating women's access and utilization of the aforementioned direct determinants (Ogundana et al., 2022).

The *mega* level was added, by extending the *meso* and *macro* layers, to consider the gender barriers at a global level (Sundermeier et al., 2018) due to the faster pace of globalization driven by technology advancements. This broader level of analysis might also include the study of emerging space entrepreneurship and its barriers (Lamine et al., 2021).

Fig. 1 The 5by5 Gender Barriers Framework for Women's Entrepreneurship

Source: Author's elaboration

Focusing, by way of example, on the segment of the framework related to financial barriers (Money) the five levels of analysis represented by the concentric circles could refer to:

- 1) *Mini level* (entrepreneur): bootstrapping and personal savings
- 2) *Micro level* (family): seeds funds from informal investors such as friends and family

- 3) *Meso level*: funds deriving from acceleration, incubators, and grants
- 4) *Macro level*: funds from Business Angels, Venture Capitalist, Private equity, and national grants
- 5) *Mega level*: crowdfunding and online crowdfunding.

The 5by5 framework can be a useful model to have a holistic understanding of the interplay of different types and level of barriers.

4. Individual barriers: lack of entrepreneurial competencies

The 5by5 framework can be adopted as conceptual model to frame the individual barriers of women entrepreneurs and to understand how the removal of these barriers, through competency development, can help overcome other gender barriers that might generate a domino effect.

The entrepreneurship literature has thoroughly examined the importance of the entrepreneur's competencies for expansion and performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), but less attention has been given to competencies and their development in women entrepreneurs specifically (Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2013; Revell-Love & Revell-Love, 2016).

Competency development of women entrepreneurs can play an important role in helping them to remove venture barriers, identified by the 5by5 Framework, such as, money, market and management barriers.

Women entrepreneurs are especially concerned about barriers to access to finance and growth capital (Elam et al., 2021) and their networking competency and self-confidence can play an important role in their ability to access financial capital (Carter & Ram, 2003; Fielden & Dawe, 2004). Male-dominated networks can constrain access to financial capital, money, but also to markets for female entrepreneurs (Brush et al. 2009).

The removal of financial barriers, through the development of specific competencies, can therefore have a ripple effect on market and management barriers. Overcoming venture barriers to female entrepreneurship promotes gender equality that contributes to economic growth (Carter et al., 2015), generating beneficial effects on different layers of society.

Drawing inspiration from the EntreComp Framework, a European framework which focuses on the development of entrepreneurial competence (Bacigalupo et al., 2016), competencies that can be particularly useful to overcome financial, market and management barriers are: *1.1 Spotting opportunities, 2.1 Self-awareness and self-efficacy, 2.4 Financial and economic literacy, s, 2.3 Mobilizing resources, 3.4 Working with others (networking).*

To identify the specific competencies helpful to overcome different types of gender barriers, however, this work suggests conducting empirical research adopting the Behavioral Event Interview (BEI) methodology, that is based on a modification of Flanagan's critical incident interview (Flanagan, 1954). The BEI technique can be particularly useful for identifying competencies that successful women entrepreneurs adopted to overcome specific gender barriers.

BEIs collect critical incidents that can be focused, in this case, on gender barriers to entrepreneurship and document what the respondent was thinking, feeling, and doing during the event (Rothwell & Lindholm, 1999). The qualitative data collected from the BEIs can be coded using thematic analysis, as suggested by Boyatzis (1998).

Through the study of competencies of particularly successful women entrepreneurs, it will be possible to design public policy and entrepreneurship programs to promote the development of specific competencies, adopting a competency-based approach to entrepreneurship education (Morris et al., 2013).

5. Implications on policy implementation and female entrepreneurship

This framework can help researchers, educators and policy makers gain a holistic understanding of women's entrepreneurship. Understanding relationships among various types and levels of barriers to women's entrepreneurship could help with the identification and attempted removal of barriers, generating a ripple effect that may improve efforts to reduce the gender gap.

Removal of individual barriers, developing "skilled and capable" (Bates et al., 2007, p. 10) women entrepreneurs, can act as a centrifugal force while institutional actions to remove gender barriers, may act as centripetal forces influencing and removing barriers at the individual level.

To encourage and enable women to overcome barriers to start and run their own business ventures, public policy and educational programs need to focus specifically on developing competencies related to entrepreneurship, especially through activities that create confidence (Brush et al., 2017; Kirkwood, 2009).

To develop self-confidence and perceived competencies in women entrepreneurs, experiential entrepreneurship programs can be particularly effective, being based on mastery experiences and "learning by doing" (Wilson et al., 2008). Entrepreneurship programs should also use storytelling as a vehicle for creating role models and enhance women confidence to grow and scale (Brush & Greene, 2020).

Another important strategy for encouraging women to start and run successful companies is to provide access to business and executive coaches. Coaching can contribute to foster the development of competencies, such as self-awareness, self-efficacy and interpersonal skills (Brinkley & Le Roux, 2018; Mineur, 2012; Saadaoui & Affess, 2015). Executive coaches can also act as network brokers, providing

entrepreneurs with access to their relevant networks and informing them about events and workshops relevant for establishing contacts (Kotte et al., 2021).

It is important that removing individual barriers for women entrepreneurs is assisted by overcoming barriers at the institutional and societal levels, through the synergistic action of investors, policy makers, entrepreneurship educators, researchers, and ecosystem supporters (Brush & Greene, 2020).

6. Applicability of the framework to different contexts

This work adopted a constructionist perspective, considering the specificity of the possible contexts in which entrepreneurship takes place. High-profile global and international studies on gender gaps were also considered to construct the 5by5 framework, which thus considers all possible types of barriers that may be present with varying intensity in different contexts and realities.

This framework can also be adopted for studying entrepreneurship in developing economies and in poverty contexts and to understand barriers that minority and immigrant entrepreneurs face.

Most of the gender barriers to entrepreneurship identified by the 5by5 framework can be also experienced by male entrepreneurs and are not always due to gender issues. Thus, this framework could be also useful in future studies on entrepreneurship barriers in general.

7. Conclusion

This paper presents a new dynamic gender-barriers framework to women' entrepreneurship that provides a springboard for future research and policy with the aim to contribute to mitigate gender gap.

Entrepreneurs, researcher, policymakers and other ecosystem supporters play an active role in constructing the context (Welter, 2020) and can therefore contribute effectively to the removal of gender barriers to entrepreneurship.

Only a set of coordinated and coherent actions at individual and societal levels, can act synergically as centrifugal and centripetal forces and can enable the removal of long-term gender barriers, creating a trajectory towards real gender equality.

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References

- Ahl, H. (2006). Why Research on Women Entrepreneurs Needs New Directions. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 595–621.
- Bacigalupo, M., Kampylis, P., Punie, Y., & Van den Brande, G. (2016). EntreComp: The Entrepreneurship Competence Framework. In *Eur 27939 En* (Issue June).
- Bates, T., Jackson, W. E., & Johnson, J. H. (2007). Advancing Research on Minority Entrepreneurship. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 612(2), 10–17.
- Boyatzis, R. E. (1998). *Transforming Qualitative Information: Thematic Analysis and Code Development*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Brinkley, M.-L., & Le Roux, I. (2018). Coaching as a Support Function for Potential Entrepreneurs. *The Southern African Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management*, 10(1), 1–12.
- Brush, C., Ali, A., Kelley, D., & Greene, P. (2017). The Influence of Human Capital Factors and Context on Women’s Entrepreneurship: Which Matters more? *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 8(April), 105–113.
- Brush, C. G., de Bruin, A., & Welter, F. (2009). A Gender-aware Framework for Women’s Entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 8–24.
- Brush, C. G., & Greene, P. G. (2020). Catalyzing Change in Equity Investing: Disruptive Models for Financing Women’s Entrepreneurship. *Diana International Impact Report, January*, 1–52.
- Burnham, J. F. (2006). Scopus Database: A Review. *Biomedical Digital Libraries*, 3, 1–8.
- Carter, S., Mwaura, S., Ram, M., Trehan, K., & Jones, T. (2015). Barriers to Ethnic

- Minority and Women's Enterprise: Existing Evidence, Policy Tensions and Unsettled Questions. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 33(1), 49–69.
- Carter, S., & Ram, M. (2003). Reassessing Portfolio Entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*, 21(4), 371–380.
- El Tarabishy, A. (2022, March 19). War & Entrepreneurship. *Small Business Horizon*.
https://smallbusinesshorizon.com/war/?mc_cid=acba7539fd&mc_eid=6effcb12fa
- Elam, A. B., Hughes, K. D., Guerrero, M., & Nawangpalupi, C. (2021). *Women's Entrepreneurship 2020/21 Thriving Through Crisis*.
- European Commission. (2020). A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025. *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions*, 1–20. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0152&from=EN>
- Fielden, S. L., & Dawe, A. (2004). Entrepreneurship and Social Inclusion. *Women in Management Review*, 19(3), 139–142.
- Flanagan, J. C. (1954). The Critical Incident Technique. *Psychological Bulletin*, 51(4), 327–358.
- Greene, P. G., Hart, M. M., Gatewood, E. J., Brush, C. G., & Carter, N. M. (2003). Women Entrepreneurs: Moving Front and Center: An Overview of Research and Theory. *Coleman White Paper Series*, 3(January), 1–47. www.usasbe.org
- Kirkwood, J. (2009). Is a Lack of Self-confidence Hindering Women Entrepreneurs? *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2), 118–133.
- Kotte, S., Diermann, I., Rosing, K., & Möller, H. (2021). Entrepreneurial Coaching: A Two-Dimensional Framework in Context. *Applied Psychology*, 70(2), 518–555.

- Lakomaa, E. (2017). The History of Business and War: Introduction. *Scandinavian Economic History Review*, 65(3), 224–230.
- Lamine, W., Anderson, A., Jack, S. L., & Fayolle, A. (2021). Entrepreneurial Space and the Freedom for Entrepreneurship: Institutional Settings, Policy, and Action in the Space Industry. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 15(2), 309–340.
- Mineur, M. (2012). *Determining Relevant Factors of Coaching: The Development of a Questionnaire*.
- Mitchelmore, S., & Rowley, J. (2013). Entrepreneurial Competencies of Women Entrepreneurs Pursuing Business Growth. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(1), 125–142.
- Morris, M. H., Webb, J. W., Fu, J., & Singhal, S. (2013). A Competency-based Perspective on Entrepreneurship Education: Conceptual and Empirical Insights.
- Ogundana, O., Simba, A., Dana, L., Liguori, E., & Dana, L. (2022). A Growth Model for Understanding Female-owned Enterprises. *Journal of the International Council for Small Business*, 1–10.
- Ogundana, O., Simba, A., Dana, L. P., & Liguori, E. (2021). Women Entrepreneurship in Developing Economies: A Gender-based Growth Model. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 59(sup1), S42–S72.
- Pittaway, L. (2021). Entrepreneurship Theory and Ideation Techniques. In *Entrepreneurial Education Research* (Vol 23).
- Pugalia, S., & Cetindamar, D. (2021). Insights on the Glass Ceiling for Immigrant Women entrepreneurs in the Technology Sector. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*.
- Revell-Love, C., & Revell-Love, T. (2016). Competencies of Women Entrepreneurs Utilizing Information Marketing Businesses. *Journal of Small Business and*

- Enterprise Development*, 23(3), 831–853.
- Rothwell, W. J., & Lindholm, J. E. (1999). Competency Identification, Modelling and Assessment in the USA. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 3(2), 90–105.
- Saadaoui, S., & Affess, H. (2015). Evaluating the Role of Coaching on Developing Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(11), 54–61.
- Strawser, J. A., Hechavarría, D. M., & Passerini, K. (2021). Gender and Entrepreneurship: Research Frameworks, Barriers and Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurship Worldwide. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 59(sup1), S1–S15.
- Sullivan, D. M., & Meek, W. R. (2012). Gender and Entrepreneurship: A review and Process Model. In *Journal of Managerial Psychology* (Vol. 27, Issue 5).
- Sundermeier, J., Wessel, L., & Davidson, E. J. (2018). Can Digital Innovation Alter the Landscape of Women's Entrepreneurship? Towards a Research Agenda. *International Conference on Information Systems 2018, ICIS 2018, September 2018*.
- Welter, F. (2020). Contexts and Gender – Looking back and Thinking forward. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 12(1), 27–38.
- Welter, F., & Smallbone, D. (2008). Women's Entrepreneurship from an Institutional Perspective: the Case of Uzbekistan. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 4(4), 505–520.
- Wheadon, M., & Duval-Couetil, N. (2019). Token Entrepreneurs: a Review of Gender, Capital, and Context in Technology Entrepreneurship. In *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development* (Vol. 31, Issues 3–4, pp. 308–336).
- Wilson, D., Kickul, J., & Marlino, D. (2008). Entrepreneurial Intentions Research :

Implications for Entrepreneurship Education. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 11(617), 87–99.

World Economic Forum. (2021). Global Gender Gap Report 2021. In *World Economic Forum* (Issue March).